

THE PERSON AND NATURES OF CHRIST: HYPOSTATIC UNION

by

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Two-thirds of Americans think that Jesus Christ is not God; they consider him merely a great teacher, as revealed by the survey “State of Theology” by Ligonier’s ministries. Surprisingly, a third of evangelical respondents in the US agree that Jesus Christ is not God.¹ The true identity, nature, and person of Christ is not only unknown among the unreached places in the world but also in the countries where Christianity is well established and practiced. In this cultural context, it is important to teach, preach, and defend the true identity, person, and nature of Jesus Christ.

The true person and nature of Christ has always been attacked ever since the birth of the church. Arianism attacked the divine nature of Christ, Apollinaris misrepresented the human nature of Christ, Nestorianism presented a malignant person of Christ, and the religious pluralism reduced the truth of incarnation to a myth and described Christ as a metaphor. The internal heresies were a major threat to the sanctity of the orthodox faith in addition to the external attacks. Despite these inaccurate representations, scripture clearly teaches two natures of the incarnated Son without contradiction (hypostatic union). When the authors of the New Testament presented the incarnation of Christ, they witnessed the incarnated Son; they clearly represented a divine Son who is co-substantial with the Father and who also humbled himself in taking human identity at the time of incarnation. Therefore, the eternal divine attributes of Christ and his human characteristics must be acknowledged together and proclaimed.

In this article, first, some of the heretical views are scrutinized through the lenses of scriptures, and their validity is assessed with the help of biblical theology, writings of church fathers, and Orthodox Christian tradition. Then, the biblical warrant for the incarnation of God

¹ The State of Theology, “The State of Theology,” accessed December 05, 2020, <https://thestateoftheology.com/>.

the Son, the second person of the Trinity, will be provided. The biblical data on the two natures of Christ, both his divine and human natures, will be discussed, and the biblical data on how the two natures exist in one person (hypostatic union) will be presented. This biblical foundation is further supported by the ecclesiastical warrant. At last, the emphasis on the mystery of the two natures in one person will be affirmed without confusing or minimizing any of the aspects of his natures. It helps to see the beauty of the dazzling portrait of Jesus Christ of the Bible against the backdrop of distorted views.

Arianism

In its earlier stage, the church struggled to formulate the doctrines of the true nature and person of Christ. However, the church soon understood its necessity due to the heretical views. Arianism is one of the earliest heretical teachings that the church survived. Arius (250-336) was a strong proponent of monotheism. However, he denied the divinity of Christ and reduced Christ to a creature level. He argued that the Father is eternal, but the Son is not eternal. The Son had a beginning at the time of creation. In this view, the Son is the principle of all creatures, and after the creation of the Son, God adopted him.² The key arguments of Arius include the following: the Son did not exist before the Father; therefore, there was a time when the Son did not exist, and the Son was derived from the Father. He implied that the son outranks other creatures. Arius argued that God the Father is unknowable; hence, the Son does not know him. He insisted that the divine title “Son” is merely an honorific title; it does not represent the divinity of Christ. Arius refuted the biblical passages that speak about the divinity of Christ. McGrath summarized Arius's position as follows:

1. The son is a creature, who, like all other creatures, derives from the will of God. 2. The

² Jean Galot, *Who Is Christ?: A Theology of the Incarnation* (Chicago, IL: Franciscan Herald Press, 1981), 227.

term “Son” is thus a metaphor, a honorific term intended to underscore the rank of the Son among other creatures. It does not imply that Father and Son share the same being or status. 3. The status of the Son is itself a consequence of the will of the Father....³

Apollinarianism

Apollinarius proposed that Christ did not have a human mind (*nous*) or rational soul (*psyche logike*) because it was supplied by the divine *Logos*.⁴ The divine *Logos* inherited only human flesh (*soma*) and animal soul (*psyche*). He argued that Christ inherited human nature but not the human mind; therefore, he should not be considered as a human individual. He strongly emphasized that “...he is one nature, one energy, one person, and one hypostasis at once wholly God and wholly man.” He questioned the existence of two separate principles of mind and will without strife. He argued that Christ never inherited a human mind because the human mind is sinful. In spite of his confession of the human nature of Christ, he clearly denied the human nature of Christ as he denied the presence of the human mind and spirit. Donald Macleod explained the Christ of Apollinarius:

Apollinarius’ Christ was truncated Christ. ‘He is not man,’ he wrote, ‘though like man; for He is not consubstantial with man in the most important element.’ At best, he is man only titularly, for He is divine spirit united to flesh’. Indeed, according to some of Apollinarius’ statements, Christ is neither God nor man but a *tertium quid*, ‘a mean between God and man.’ On occasion, he speaks of the qualities of the two natures as being ‘mixed’ or ‘commingled’, but this always leaves the divine nature unaffected. There is no real incarnation, no assumption of humanity and no becoming of man. There is only God assuming the conditions of human existence. In that existence the human body and the divine *Logos* formed one *ousia*, but there was no room for a human psychology.⁵

³ Alister E. McGrath, *Historical Theology: An Introduction to the History of Christian Thought* (Oxford: Blackwell, 1998), 48-49.

⁴ Philip Jenkins, *Jesus Wars: How Four Patriarchs, Three Queens, and Two Emperors Decided What Christians Would Believe for the Next 1,500 Years*, 1st ed. (New York: HarperOne, 2010), 53-54.

⁵ Donald Macleod, *The Person of Christ. Contours of Christian Theology*, (Leicester, England: Inter-Varsity Press, PC, 1998), 158-159.

Nestorianism

Nestorianism is a heresy that proposed that there are two separate persons in Christ, one divine and one human. Nestorius rejected the title “*Theotokos*,” “Mother of God,” for Mary and insisted on the use of “*Christotokos*,” or “Mother of Christ.” He faced severe opposition because the title “*Theotokos*” was used by the majority of the theologians, including Alexander of Alexandria. He asserted that it is not proper to say *Logos* was born of Mary. In spite of the accusations against Nestorius, there is also a disagreement on whether Nestorius was Nestorian. His failure to distinguish nature from the concept of person stemmed the controversy. Nestorius understood that *prosopon* to be the appearance of essence. He argued that each of the two natures in Christ had a different *hypostasis*.⁶ Galot explained the position of Nestorius accurately:

Now, for Nestorius the unity of this *prosopon* is realized by the compensation of the *prospa*, that is to say, by an exchange of appearances, inasmuch as the Son uses a human *prosopon* to represent him and the human *prosopon* receives a glorious divine form. This unity is realized by a mutual compenetration (perichoresis) of the *prosopa*. The compenetration occurs through the indwelling of the Word in the man as in a temple. Nestorius even spoke of two natures without confusion, namely, God-made-man and man made into God.⁷

Hick’s Myth and Metaphor

Religious pluralists distorted the true meaning and purpose of the incarnation of Christ. They did not affirm the literal virgin birth or resurrection of Christ. John Hick attempted to refute the orthodox understanding of the true nature of Christ. He argued that incarnation is a myth but it could serve as a metaphor. He insists that “...Jesus was a man, whose immensely powerful God-consciousness made God....” He argues that Jesus did not intend to establish a church or

⁶ According to Nestorius, *hypostasis* do not imply a person. On the other hand, he believed that there was a union of two natures to form a whole *prosopon*, the common *prosopon* of Jesus Christ. Galot, *Who Is Christ?*, 240.

⁷ Galot, *Who Is Christ?*, 240.

religion, and he was mistaken in his expectation.⁸ He also argued against the orthodox understanding of two natures and one person and questioned the explanations given by the councils and evangelicals. The nature of Christ with two minds would not give a satisfactory explanation of the incarnation of the Son, and it is at best not superior to the two-substances view of Christ. He insisted that the story of the incarnation of Jesus is acceptable as a metaphor. He explained his position as follows:

In the case of the metaphor of divine incarnation, what was lived out, made flesh, incarnated in the life of Jesus can be indicated in at least three ways, each of which is an aspect of the fact that Jesus was a human being exceptionally open and responsive to the divine presence: 1) In so far as Jesus was doing God's will, God was acting through him on earth and was in this respect 'incarnate' in Jesus' life; (2) In so far as Jesus was doing God's will he 'incarnated' the ideal of human life lived in openness and response to God; (3) In so far as Jesus lived a life of self-giving love, or *agape*, he 'incarnated' a love that is a finite reflection of the infinite divine love.⁹

Hypostatic Union of God the Son Incarnate

Scripture clearly teaches the eternal pre-existence of Christ and his literal incarnation. Christ, being the second person of the Trinity, always existed before the foundation of the world. In the Gospel of John, it is evident that the Son, the divine *Logos*, was presented as an eternal person who took the form of human nature when he incarnated in a specific time and space and identified himself with human beings. In John 1:1, John proclaimed that "In the beginning was the Word, and the Word was with God, and the Word was God (ESV)." It is evident that the divine *Logos*, the Son, was never created; rather, he always eternally existed with the Father. The divine *Logos* was clearly identified as God along with the Father.¹⁰

⁸ John Hick, *The Metaphor of God Incarnate: Christology in a Pluralistic Age*, 2nd ed, (Louisville, KY: Westminster John Knox Press, 2006), 26.

⁹ Hick, *The Metaphor of God Incarnate*, 26.

¹⁰ Macleod, *The Person of Christ*, 45-46.

John developed the theme of incarnation and proclaimed that the eternal Son later took the form of humanity. In John 1:14, he said, “And the Word became flesh and dwelt among us (ESV).” It is evident that the Son was not eternally in the form of flesh; rather, he became flesh and dwelt among humans at a certain point.¹¹ It is important to emphasize that the Son did not merely appear as a human; rather, he literally became flesh so that he could truly become one of us to represent humanity. John clearly depicted the eternal pre-existence of Christ throughout the Gospel (John 1:18, 8:58, and 17:5). The authors of the New Testament celebrated the incarnation of the prophesied divine King Messiah. In Matthew 1:23, the author alluded to the prophecy “Behold, the virgin shall conceive and bear a son, and they shall call his name Immanuel (ESV).” The conception was understood to be literal fulfillment. There was no hint of myth or legend. The specifics of details like birthplace, parents, geographical location, and context of the political situation were recorded. The other authors of the New Testament witnessed and signified the incarnation of Christ (Luke 1:35, Phil. 2:5-7, and 1 Tim. 3:16).

In his book “God the Son Incarnate,” Wellum demonstrated the divinity of Christ in the categories of divine status, divine works, and divine titles.¹² Jesus Christ possessed the divine attributes, divine authority, and worthiness of worship.¹³ The incarnated Son possessed omniscience (Mark 2:8, John 1:48, 2:25, 6:64, 21:17, Acts 1:24, 1 Cor. 4:5, and Col. 2:3), omnipotence (Matt. 8:26-27, 1 Cor. 1:18, Eph. 1:19-20, and Col. 2:10), omnipresence (Matt. 18:20, 28:20, and Eph. 4:10), and immutability (Heb. 1:10-12, 13:8, and James 1:17).¹⁴ The incarnated Son exercises the divine authority and rules over all the creation (Rom. 14:9, 1 Cor.

¹¹ Macleod, 46.

¹²Stephen J. Wellum, *God the Son Incarnate: The Doctrine of Christ*, Foundations of Evangelical Theology Series, (Wheaton, Illinois: Crossway, 2016),192.

¹³ Wellum, 192.

¹⁴ Wellum, 193.

15:27-28, Eph. 1:21, and 1 Peter 3:22) and sits on God's throne (2 Cor. 5:10, Heb. 1:3, and Revelation 22:1).¹⁵ The incarnated Son was worshipped by the monotheistic Jewish disciples, and he accepted their worship (Mat. 14:33, 28:9, and John 20:28).¹⁶ The incarnated Son had the authority to forgive sins (Mark 2:10 and Acts 5:31) and raised the people who were dead (Mark 5:21-24, Luke 7:11-17, and John 11:1-14).¹⁷ The authors of the New Testament ascribed the divine title "Lord" (*Kurios*) to the incarnated Son to identify him with Yahweh (John 8:58, Rev. 1:17, Rom. 9:33, and 1 Peter 2:6).¹⁸ They did not shy away from applying the divine title "God" (*Theos*) to the Son of God (John 1:1, 18; 20:28; Rom. 9:5; Titus 2:13; 2 Pet. 1:1; and Heb. 1:8).¹⁹

The humanity of the incarnated Son is equally important as his divinity. Gregory of Nazianzus pointed out "that which is not assumed is not healed."²⁰ The human identity and nature of Jesus Christ are essential to represent humanity in order to bring salvation to mankind. In spite of his human nature, Christ was without sin, as sin is not essential for human nature.²¹ Jesus was born as a human baby (Luke 2:7) and grew as a child to adulthood (Luke 2:40). He possessed the full nature of humanity and experienced human needs. He experienced tiredness, thirst, and hunger as any other human being (John 4:6, 19:28, and Matt. 4:2). He experienced death as a human being (Luke 23:46) and resurrected bodily with a physical human body (Luke

¹⁵ Wellum, 194.

¹⁶ Wellum, 195.

¹⁷ Wellum, 199.

¹⁸ Wellum, *God the Son Incarnate*, 200.

¹⁹ Wellum, 201.

²⁰ Wellum, 232.

²¹ Wayne A. Grudem, *Systematic Theology: An Introduction to Biblical Doctrine* (Leicester, England: Inter-Varsity Press, 1994), 889.

24:39).²² Jesus had a human mind (Luke 2:52) and a human soul or spirit (John 12:27 and 13:21).²³

Scripture clearly presents two natures of Christ, and it does not present him as one person. At the same time, no indication of blending of the natures or multiple persons was mentioned. Both human and divine natures were preserved without contradiction. In Romans 9:5, Paul revealed two natures of Christ in one person: "...to them belong the patriarchs, and from their race, according to the flesh, is the Christ who is God over all..." (ESV). In Colossians 2:9, Paul taught that "for in him the whole fullness of deity dwells bodily (ESV)." In this text, the presence of divine nature was clearly identified with human nature, and yet there was no indication of alteration or change of any of the natures. The word "fullness of deity" also signifies that the divine nature was not compromised; therefore it avoids speculation of emanation or a secondary level of divine nature. The presence of God now dwelt "bodily," which contradicts the assumption of Docetism and Apollinarianism. In spite of the presence of full deity in the body, he was referred to as one person ("in him").

The authors of the New Testament did not use any specific technical term to describe the two natures in one person. However, the church formulated the phrase "*hypostatic union*" to understand the two natures of Christ in one person (Gk. *hypostasis*).²⁴ The term "hypostatic union" summarizes three facts: Christ is one person; the union between the human and divine natures belongs to the same person, and this one person, the incarnated Son, is the agent behind

²² Grudem, 532.

²³ Grudem, 533.

²⁴ John M. Frame, *Systematic Theology: An Introduction to Christian Belief*, (Phillipsburg, New Jersey: P & R Publishing, 2013), 887.

all of the Lord's acts, the utterer of all his communications, and the subject of all his experiences.²⁵

The orthodox Christian tradition upheld the incarnation of Christ and his two natures in one person. The early church fathers and the ecumenical councils stood against the heretical compositions of inadequate Christs. Athanasius of Alexandria (c. 293-373) affirmed that the incorporeal, incorruptible, and immaterial divine *Logos* entered into the realm of humans, although he was never detached from us. He affirmed the omnipresence of the Son and his presence with the Father.²⁶ He emphasized the divine *Logos* incarnated into a body and lived as a human; however, he never left his divinity and knowledge.²⁷ The Council of Nicaea in 325 affirmed the divine nature of Christ and affirmed that Christ was not begotten but rather begotten of the same substance (*homoousios*) as the Father. It also condemned the teachings of Arius. Although the Church affirmed both natures, it struggled to formulate the doctrine of two natures in one person until it approved the statement of the Council of Chalcedon in 451. The Council affirmed that Christ is consubstantial with the Father in Godhead and consubstantial with humanity. It also affirmed that the two natures were acknowledged without confusion, without change, without division, and without separation. It affirmed that the two natures were combined in person and *hypostasis*.²⁸

Evaluation of Arguments

The church witnessed inadequate portrayals of Christ's incarnation and his true nature. The heretical and pluralistic teachings are not supported by the Scriptures. They were rejected as

²⁵ Macleod, *The Person of Christ*, 189.

²⁶ Athanasius, and John Behr., *On the Incarnation*. Popular Patristics Series, (Vladimir's Seminary Press, 2011), 56.

²⁷ Athanasius, 98.

²⁸ Wellum, *God the Son Incarnate*, 303.

unorthodox teachings by the church tradition and ecumenical councils. Arianism denies the divinity of Christ and his eternal existence with the Father. It reduces Christ to a creature, and it insists that “Christ is changeable or alterable.” Although Arianism appeals to the scriptures, in affirming the oneness of God, it fails to portray Christ as the divine incarnated Son. Scripture clearly teaches that Christ, the divine *Logos*, was present in the beginning with God the Father, and the divine *Logos* himself was identified as God (John 1:1-3). The eternal pre-existence of Christ, his divine attributes, titles, and actions set him apart as God-man, the incarnated Son (John 1:18, 8:58, 17:5; Mark 2:8; John 1:48, 2:25, 6:64, 21:17; Acts 1:24; 1 Cor. 4:5; Col. 2:3; Matt. 8:26-27; 1 Cor. 1:18; Eph. 1:19-20; Col. 2:10; Matt. 18:20, 28:20; Eph. 4:10; Heb. 1:10-12, 13:8; and James 1:17).

While Arianism denied the divinity of Christ in the defense of the Trinity, Apollinarianism rejected the full humanity of Christ, and Nestorianism promoted two persons in Christ. Apollinaris suggested that Christ did not have a human mind (*nous*) and rational soul (*psyche logike*). The scriptures clearly present Christ as a true human with all the human faculties, including a human mind and soul with human capacities (Luke 2:52, John 12:27, and 13:21). The Christ of Apollinaris is inadequate to represent the true humanity to redeem mankind. Similarly, Nestorius rejected the title “*theotokos*” and refused to describe Jesus as God. Nestorianism further developed a non-orthodox teaching of two different persons in Christ and their union. It is not only supported by the scriptural data, but it is also problematic in preserving the two natures of Christ and his personhood. In Colossians 2:9, Paul teaches that “for in him the whole fullness of deity dwells bodily (ESV).” In this text, the presence of divine nature was clearly identified with the human nature, and yet there was no indication of alteration or change of any of the natures. In spite of the presence of full deity in the body, he was referred to as one

person (“in him”). Scripture clearly presented the divine nature and attributes of Christ along with his incarnated human nature. However, scriptures never described two persons in Christ. Whenever the authors of the New Testament presented Christ, they portrayed him as one person, the incarnated Son, Lord Jesus Christ. The ontological Christology has its implications in understanding the salvation history. It emphasizes the need of a savior who could redeem and restore the fallen man.

John Hick was a religious pluralist who did not accept the exclusive claims of Christian faith. Hick denied the literal sense of the incarnation of Christ and advocated that the incarnation could be understood as a metaphor. According to him, Christ is an ideal of human life, self-giving love, and a finite expression of infinite God. Although Hick highlighted the dimension of moral perfectness and love of Christ, he clearly undercut the true person of Christ. Although Jesus Christ was a perfect man and moral teacher who left an example for humanity, certainly, he is more than that. Scriptures revealed Christ as God the Son, incarnated to identify with humans to represent them, died and resurrected for their salvation, and ascended into heaven to reign with the Father. He denied the authority of scriptures by undermining the divinity of Christ and rejecting the full presentation of Christ in scriptures and the witness of apostles. As Wellum observed, Hick’s prior commitment to pluralism made it difficult for him to see the true identity of Christ as revealed in the scriptures.²⁹ The incarnation of Christ is well attested by the evidence of the New Testament and the witness of early monotheistic Jewish disciples who accepted Christianity. However, as Wellum pointed out, only Christology from above—God’s own revelatory interpretation—reveals the true person and nature of Christ.³⁰

²⁹ Wellum, *God the Son Incarnate*, 44.

³⁰ Wellum, 95.

The common objections to the orthodox formulation of Chalcedon Christology (two natures in one person) include the usage of Greek philosophical terminology (like *ousia* and *hypostasis*) and the problem of two wills. The critics point out that metaphysical speculation of Christ's identity is inadequate to explain the mystery of incarnation. Wellum defended the stance of usage of the technical Greek phrases in explaining the theological concepts. He argued that theologizing demands a need for such terminology. He argued that Chalcedon employed the terms in an un-Greek way to present the biblical concepts.³¹ Some theologians argue that the formulation of two natures in one person results in the confusion of the two wills of Christ and thereby his natures.³² The correct understanding of the distinction between person and nature would resolve the tension. The person of Christ, the divine Son, acts through his natures. It is the person who acts, but through the faculties of his nature.³³

The heretical views of Arianism, Apollinarianism, Nestorianism, and Hick's pluralistic view of metaphor lack the biblical warrant and fail to represent the true identity of Jesus Christ. These explanations failed to reflect the divine and human natures of Christ; therefore, they do not represent the big picture of the incarnated Son. On the other hand, scripture clearly presents Jesus Christ as the incarnated Son, his two natures as God and man in one person (hypostatic union). The witness of scripture is well attested by the church tradition. The church affirmed that Christ is God from God, and his two natures were acknowledged without confusion, without change, without division, and as one person without separation.³⁴ Macleod explained the person of Christ in a thoughtful way:

³¹ Wellum, 308.

³² Wellum, 338.

³³ Wellum, 343.

³⁴ Grudem, *Systematic Theology*, 554.

This means that whenever we look at the life of Christ and ask, Who did this? Who suffered this? Who suffered this? Who said this? the answer is always the same: ‘The Son of God!’ We can never say, ‘The divine nature did this!’ or, ‘The human nature did this!’ We must say, ‘He did this: he, the Son of God!’ He was born, baptized, tempted, and transfigured. ...He was flogged, immolated, crucified, dead, and buried. He rose from the dead. He reigns. ...In him, God adds human being to his divine being and human experience to his divine experience. In him, God lives a truly human existence. This is the heart of the miracle of incarnation: the Son of God ‘exists not only in heavenly form, but also in earthly-historical form.’³⁵

Conclusion

The true nature and person of Christ is always misunderstood. The heretical views of Arianism, Apollinarianism, Nestorianism, and Hick’s pluralistic view of metaphor lack the biblical warrant and fail to represent the true identity of Jesus Christ. Despite the confusing attempts of heresies, the orthodox Christian tradition confessed that Christ is the incarnated Son of God, he is truly God and truly human. The church affirmed that Christ is God from God, and his two natures were acknowledged without confusion, without change, and without division, and as one person without separation.³⁶ This fundamental truth is well attested by the scriptures and confessed by the church councils. In this secular context of religious pluralism, the true identity, nature, and person of Jesus Christ should be preached, proclaimed, and defended.

³⁵ Macleod, *The Person of Christ*, 189-190.

³⁶ Grudem, *Systematic Theology*, 554.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Athanasius, and John Behr. *On the Incarnation*. Popular Patristics Series. Yonkers, N.Y.: St Vladimir's Seminary Press, 2011.
- Frame, John M. *Systematic Theology: An Introduction to Christian Belief*. Phillipsburg, New Jersey: P & R Publishing, 2013.
- Galot, Jean. *Who Is Christ?: A Theology of the Incarnation*. Chicago, IL: Franciscan Herald Press, 1981.
- Grudem, Wayne A. *Systematic Theology: An Introduction to Biblical Doctrine*. Leicester, England: Inter-Varsity Press, 1994.
- Hick, John. *The Metaphor of God Incarnate: Christology in a Pluralistic Age*. 2nd ed. Louisville, Ky.: Westminster John Knox Press, 2006.
- Jenkins, Philip. *Jesus Wars: How Four Patriarchs, Three Queens, and Two Emperors Decided What Christians Would Believe for the Next 1,500 Years*. 1st ed. New York: HarperOne, 2010.
- Macleod, Donald. *The Person of Christ. Contours of Christian Theology*. Leicester, England: Inter-Varsity Press, 1998.
- McGrath, Alister E. *Historical Theology: An Introduction to the History of Christian Thought*. Oxford: Blackwell, 1998.
- The State of Theology. “*The State of Theology*.” Accessed December 05, 2020. <https://thestateoftheology.com/>.
- Wellum, Stephen J. *God the Son Incarnate: The Doctrine of Christ*. Foundations of Evangelical Theology Series. Wheaton, Illinois: Crossway, 2016.